

1 **Principal Component Analysis to Determine the Surface Properties that Influence the**
2 **Self-Cleaning Action of Hydrophobic Plant Leaves**

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23 **ABSTRACT**

24 It is well established that many leaf surfaces display self-cleaning properties. However, an
25 understanding of how the surface properties interact is still confounding. Consequently, twelve
26 different leaf types were selected for analysis due to their water repellency and self-cleaning
27 properties. The most hydrophobic surfaces demonstrated splitting of the ν_s CH₂ and ν CH₂
28 bands, ordered platelet-like structures, crystalline waxes, high surface roughness values, high
29 total surface free energy and apolar components of surface energy, and low polar and Lewis
30 base components of surface energy. The surfaces that exhibited the least roughness and high
31 polar and Lewis base components of surface energy had intracuticular waxes, yet still
32 demonstrated self-cleaning action. Principal component analysis demonstrated that the most
33 hydrophobic species shared common surface chemistry traits with low intra-class variability,
34 whilst the less hydrophobic leaves had highly-variable surface chemistry characteristics.
35 Despite this, we have shown through partial least squares regression that leaf water contact
36 angle (i.e. hydrophobicity) can be predicted using attenuated total reflectance Fourier transform
37 infrared spectroscopy surface chemistry data with excellent ability. This is the first time that
38 such a statistical analysis has been performed on a complex biological system. This model
39 could be utilised to investigate and predict the water contact angles of a range of biological
40 surfaces. An understanding of the interplay of properties is extremely important when
41 producing optimised biomimetic surfaces.

42

43 **Keywords:** Biomimetic; plant; roughness; superhydrophobic; wax; self-cleaning.

44

45 INTRODUCTION

46 There has been significant interest directed towards producing biomimetic surfaces
47 with controlled surface wetting properties.¹ Much of this work has concentrated on altering
48 surface topography and chemistry to produce superhydrophobic surfaces. It is generally
49 considered that the topography of plant surfaces is the main factor influencing water contact
50 angle, and hence water repellency.^{2,3} Specifically, hierarchical structures at the macro and
51 micro levels (the Lotus effect) are associated with superhydrophobicity of leaf surfaces.⁴ The
52 leaves are also self-cleaning, meaning that rolling droplets can remove microorganisms and
53 other contaminants from their surfaces. Numerous biomimetic surfaces have been developed
54 which emulate the topography of superhydrophobic leaves to achieve self-cleaning, water
55 repellency, and anticontamination properties.⁵⁻⁸ However, many self-cleaning surfaces
56 produced with biomimetic topographies still require chemical modification to exhibit
57 superhydrophobicity. Many plant surfaces are hydrophobic (WCA $>110^\circ$) or
58 superhydrophobic (WCA $>150^\circ$).⁹ However, in nature, there are also several leaf surfaces that
59 display self-cleaning and water-repellent behaviours, and yet they are not superhydrophobic
60 and may not have predominant topographical features.

61 It is well established that the wax layer on leaf surfaces, in particular epicuticular wax
62 crystals, makes an essential contribution to surface hydrophobicity.¹⁰ The chemical
63 compositions of such waxes from numerous leaf surfaces have been determined.¹¹⁻¹⁷ However,
64 the exact relationship between the surface chemistry and topography, in addition to their
65 influence on surface physiochemistry is not fully understood. Consequently, producing
66 biomimetic surfaces that maintain their anti-wetting features still presents a significant
67 challenge. Thus, an understanding of the key surface properties that result in the water
68 repellency of natural surfaces is essential to further the development of biomimetic surfaces.

69 The aim of this work was to determine the relationship between the surface topography,
70 chemistry, and physiochemistry of a selection of plant leaves that demonstrated self-cleaning
71 properties. This was implemented through a combination of complimentary experimental
72 techniques and modelling methods to identify the key parameters that resulted in the self-
73 cleaning properties of these natural surfaces. This information is vitally important to many
74 aspects of industry where producing low-cost and consistent biomimetic surfaces is a priority.

75

76 **EXPERIMENTAL**

77 *Leaf collection*

78 Plant leaves were selected based on their ability to repel water. Many leaf types were
79 sprayed with water for 1 min and then immediately assessed. Those that exhibited no residual
80 water droplets or spherical spray droplets on their surfaces were deemed the most hydrophobic,
81 and therefore selected. Leaves from the following plants were collected (Westhoughton,
82 Greater Manchester, UK) between the months of September and November 2017: *Aquilegia*
83 *vulgaris* (Aquilegia), *Citrus sinensis* (Orange), *Gladiolus hybridus* (Gladioli), *Hosta*
84 *sieboldiana* (Hosta), *Hyacinthus litwinovii* (Hyacinth), *Ilex aquifolium* (Holly), *Lathyrus*
85 *odoratus* (Sweet pea), *Lupinus polyphyllus* (Lupin), *Nymphaea odorata* (Water lily),
86 *Pelargonium graveolens* (Geranium), *Prunus laurocerasus* (Laurel), and *Rhododendron*
87 *azaleastrum* (Azalea). Leaf samples were either used within 2-4 h of harvesting or stored at 4
88 °C for a maximum of 24 h before use. The leaves were stored individually in plastic bags until
89 use to ensure that the loss of humidity from the leaf was reduced. A number of separate batches
90 of mature leaves were collected on different days over the two-month experimental period (n
91 = 10).

92

93 *Determination of surface energy components*

94 The total surface free energy (γ_s) and the apolar (γ_s^{LW}), polar (γ_s^{AB}), Lewis acid (γ_s^+),
95 and Lewis base (γ_s^-) free energy components of the adaxial surfaces of the leaves were
96 determined using contact angle goniometry. The surface energy components of the leaves were
97 calculated according to work by van Oss and colleagues.¹⁸⁻²⁰ A KRÜSS sessile drop
98 goniometer (GH11 KRÜSS, France) was used to perform the measurements with three test
99 liquids: HPLC grade water (BDH, UK), formamide (Sigma-Aldrich, UK), and diiodomethane
100 (Alfa Aesar, UK). For each plant species, except the *Rhododendron azaleastrum*, samples were
101 cut from different parts of the same leaf and attached to microscope slides using double-sided
102 adhesive tape (3M, UK). In the case of *Rhododendron azaleastrum*, individual leaves were
103 used for each test liquid. For all test liquids, the droplet volume was 5 μ L and was dispensed
104 using a micro-syringe dedicated to a single solvent.

105 For each plant species, the van Oss and Good equations were used to obtain the surface
106 energy components from the contact angles of the three test liquids on the leaf surfaces.¹⁸⁻²⁰
107 The surface free energy components of these three liquids were taken from Bos et al.²¹
108 (Supporting Information: Table S1).

109 The contact angles of each test liquid were obtained from five different areas on the
110 leaf, therefore average values were used to obtain the physicochemical parameters. The
111 statistical error in the calculated surface energy components was estimated from the contact
112 angles of each test liquid by using propagation of error principles. The interfacial free energy
113 (ΔG_{iwi}) was used as a measure of the hydrophobicity of a leaf surface where greater (negative)
114 ΔG_{iwi} values related to more hydrophobic surfaces.

115

116 *Optical profilometry and scanning electron microscopy (SEM)*

117 The surface topographies of the leaves were investigated using a previously described
118 method with a MicroXAM (phase shift) surface mapping microscope (ADE corporation, XYZ

119 model 4400 ml system, USA).²² The optical profilometer used an AD phase shift controller
120 (Omniscan, UK). A MAPVIEW AE 2.17 (Omniscan, UK) image analysis system was utilised
121 to obtain the average surface roughness (S_a), root mean square roughness (S_q), and average
122 peak-to-valley roughness (S_{pv}) (n=10).

123 SEM images were obtained using a Supra 40VP SEM (Carl Zeiss Ltd., UK) with an
124 adapted protocol.²³ The leaf samples were soaked for 24 h at 4 °C in 4 % v/v glutaraldehyde
125 (Agar Scientific, UK). The leaf samples were removed and the excess glutaraldehyde was
126 washed from the leaf surface using sterile water. The leaf samples were then dried overnight.
127 Following drying, the samples were cut into ca. 6 mm² coupons. The adaxial sides of the leaves
128 were fixed to carbon pads on SEM stubs (Agar Scientific, UK). The fixed leaf surfaces were
129 sputter coated with gold (Polaron, UK) using the parameters: 5 mA, < 0.1 mbar, and 800 V in
130 argon gas.

131

132 *Attenuated total reflectance Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (ATR-FTIR)*

133 ATR-FTIR analysis was performed on leaf samples using a Spectrum Two FT-IR
134 Spectrometer (PerkinElmer, UK) fitted with a UATR single bounce ATR accessory with a
135 diamond (refractive index 2.40) internal reflection element (IRE) (45° angle of incidence) and
136 LiTaO₃ detector. For each leaf sample, five different areas were analysed obtaining the spectra
137 over the range of 450 to 4000 cm⁻¹. Spectra were made up of four scans with the resolution set
138 to 4 cm⁻¹ and the results were expressed in absorbance. It is worth noting that the penetration
139 depth of the evanescent wave into the leaf surface from the IRE can be estimated to be 1.5 μm
140 at 2900 cm⁻¹ and 6.1 μm at 700 cm⁻¹. Calculations based on the equation by F.Mirabella
141 assumed the leaf surface to be mainly hydrocarbon, i.e. paraffin wax (refractive index 1.45).²⁴
142 Due to the topographical aspects potentially affecting contact with the IRE, the spectra were
143 not corrected for wavelength dependent penetration depth.

144

145 *Statistical analysis*

146 Error bars were representative of the standard deviation or $\pm 5\%$ error. One-way
147 analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Newman-Keuls tests were performed using R.
148 3.4.1 software. Differences between samples were considered statistically significant for p
149 values < 0.05 .

150

151 *Principal component analysis (PCA)*

152 PCA was carried out on the ATR-FTIR data measured using R (version 3.2.2, R Core
153 Team, 2015)²⁵ and R Studio (version 0.99.486, R Studio Team).²⁶ PCA analysis was performed
154 using the `prcomp` function as part of the `stats` package by singular value decomposition of the
155 centred and scaled data matrix.²⁵ Results of this analysis were visualised using the `factoextra`
156 package (version 1.0.5) and `ggplot2`.²⁷

157

158 *Partial least squares regression (PLSR)*

159 PLSR was carried out on the ATR-FTIR data using R (version 3.2.2, R Core Team,
160 2015)²⁵ and R Studio (version 0.99.486, R Studio Team, 2015).²⁶ PLSR analysis was performed
161 using the `pls` function as part of the `pls` package (version 2.7-1).²⁸ The kernel algorithm was
162 used on a mean-centred predictor and response data matrix. Leave-one-out cross-validation
163 was utilised to optimise the number of components (8) to be used in the final model.

164

165 **RESULTS**

166 *Physicochemical properties of the leaf surfaces*

167 The physicochemical parameter values are represented in radar graphs (Figure 1) to
168 provide a physicochemical map for each leaf surface. Furthermore, the physicochemical

169 parameters of the twelve leaf surfaces are presented in Table 1. The γ_s^{LW} values of all the leaves
170 were higher than their corresponding γ_s^{AB} values. Therefore, all the leaves investigated had
171 non-polar adaxial surfaces. The three most hydrophobic leaves (*Gladiolus hybridus*, *Lupinus*
172 *polyphyllus*, and *Lathyrus odoratus*) demonstrated high γ_s^{LW} values and substantially lower
173 γ_s^{AB} , γ_s^+ , and γ_s^- values. These patterns were represented in the graphs in Figure 1 by thin
174 asymmetric diamond shapes with the long arm pointing upwards. The base and short downward
175 arm of the diamond was formed from the relatively insignificant γ_s^{AB} , γ_s^+ , and γ_s^- contributions
176 to the total surface energy. The less hydrophobic surfaces had higher γ_s^- values which led to
177 graphs with wider bases and various triangular shapes.

178

179

180 **Figure 1.** Radar graphs showing the magnitude of the surface energy components for each leaf

181 type.

182

183 **Table 1.** Physicochemical parameters of the adaxial surface of the leaf samples. The values are
 184 expressed in mJ/m^2 and the errors are in parenthesis.

Leaf	ΔG_{iwi}	γ_{s}	$\gamma_{\text{s}}^{\text{LW}}$	$\gamma_{\text{s}}^{\text{AB}}$	γ_{s}^+	γ_{s}^-
<i>Lathyrus odoratus</i>	-91.7 (9.4)	11.6 (1.0)	11.6 (0.9)	0.1 (0.3)	0.0 (0.0)	0.38 (0.43)
<i>Gladiolus hybridus</i>	-91.3 (12.2)	6.0 (1.2)	5.4 (1.0)	0.6 (0.7)	0.4 (0.4)	0.25 (0.44)
<i>Lupinus polyphyllus</i>	-74.7 (10.6)	16.4 (1.4)	16.2 (0.7)	0.2 (1.2)	1.8 (0.7)	0.00 (0.06)
<i>Aquilegia vulgaris</i>	-64.2 (16.4)	6.9 (2.1)	4.2 (1.0)	2.7 (1.8)	0.4 (0.4)	4.9 (2.90)
<i>Pelargonium graveolens</i>	-54.0 (7.9)	31.5 (1.5)	28.1 (0.9)	3.4 (1.2)	3.3 (0.7)	0.9 (0.57)
<i>Nymphaea odorata</i>	-41.1 (6.5)	35.9 (1.3)	29.0 (0.9)	6.9 (1.0)	2.6 (0.5)	4.5 (1.01)
<i>Hyacinthus litwinovii</i>	-38.3 (7.9)	37.1 (1.4)	36.6 (0.6)	0.5 (1.3)	0.0 (0.0)	10.9 (1.97)
<i>Prunus laurocerasus</i>	-30.1 (6.8)	32.0 (1.2)	29.1 (0.6)	2.8 (1.1)	0.2 (0.1)	12.2 (1.91)
<i>Rhododendron azaleastrum</i>	-14.5 (11.1)	30.3 (2.3)	29.9 (0.6)	0.4 (2.2)	0.0 (0.0)	19.3 (3.76)
<i>Ilex aquifolium</i>	-6.0 (10.5)	38.8 (2.2)	31.5 (0.6)	7.3 (2.1)	0.6 (0.3)	23.1 (3.98)
<i>Hosta sieboldiana</i>	-5.7 (32.6)	32.6 (2.8)	27.6 (1.2)	5.0 (2.6)	0.3 (0.3)	22.8 (3.50)
<i>Citrus sinensis</i>	-2.3 (10.2)	36.4 (2.2)	29.0 (0.6)	7.5 (2.1)	0.6 (0.3)	24.8 (3.99)

185

186 *Surface topography*

187 The topographies of the leaves were investigated at the macro, micro, and nanoscale scale to
 188 comprehensively analyse the morphology of the surface features. Low magnification SEM
 189 images (Figure 2) revealed that the macro topographies of the leaves were most commonly
 190 characterised by platelet-type features (Figure 2a, g, j, m, p, s, ee, and hh). However, some
 191 exhibited quite different surface topographies including homogenous distributions of raised
 192 nodules (Figure 2d), subtle network structures (Figure 2v and y), and very flat, almost
 193 featureless surfaces (Figure 2bb). Optical profilometry images highlighted the micro
 194 topographies of the leaf surfaces and revealed more detailed information regarding the varied

195 platelet-like morphology. For example, the average platelet feature length ranged from 10 to
196 45 μm and some were very regular in shape (Figure 2h, n, and ff), whilst other were far more
197 irregular (Figure 2b, k, t, and ii). The nano features of the surface topographies were
198 investigated using high magnification SEM. The images demonstrated that wax nanocrystals
199 were present on all the leaf surfaces in varying amounts. The most hydrophobic surfaces
200 (Figure 2c, 2f, 2i, and 2l) exhibited dense distributions of wax nanocrystals, whilst the less
201 hydrophobic surfaces had far smaller amounts (Figure 2x, aa, dd, gg, and jj).
202

a) *Lathyrus odoratus*

b)

c)

d) *Gladiolus hybridus*

e)

f)

g) *Lupinus polyphyllus*

h)

i)

j) *Aquilegia vulgaris*

k)

l)

m) *Pelargonium graveolens*

n)

o)

p) *Nymphaea odorata*

q)

r)

s) *Hyacinthus litwinovii*

t)

u)

v) *Prunus laurocerasus*

w)

x)

y) *Rhododendron azaleastrum*

z)

aa)

bb) *Ilex aquifolium Ilex aquifolium*

cc)

dd)

ee) *Hosta sieboldiana*

ff)

gg)

hh) *Citrus sinensis*

ii)

jj)

205 **Figure 2.** Optical profilometry and SEM images of the adaxial surfaces of the leaf samples
 206 demonstrating their macro, micro, and nano surface topographies.

207

208 Table 3 presents the surface roughness values for each leaf type. The results demonstrate that
 209 the more hydrophobic surfaces generally had the greatest roughness values, whilst the least
 210 hydrophobic surfaces had the lowest roughness values. However, there were some exceptions
 211 to this trend. For example, the *Pelargonium graveolens* had the largest roughness values.
 212 Similarly, the *Hyacinthus litwinovii* leaf, which was not one of the most hydrophobic surfaces,
 213 also had large S_a (2.8 μm) and S_{pv} (118.9 μm) values. Generally, the least hydrophobic surfaces
 214 had less defined surface features. The exception was the *Hosta sieboldiana*, which had low
 215 surface roughness values but still demonstrated defined platelet-type features on its surface
 216 (Figure 2n).

217

218 **Table 3.** Surface roughness parameters of the leaf samples obtained from the optical
 219 profilometry data. The standard deviations are indicated in parenthesis.

Leaf	S_a (μm)	S_q (μm)	S_{pv} (μm)
<i>Lathyrus odoratus</i>	3.2 (0.6)	3.9 (0.7)	36.5 (8.5)
<i>Gladiolus hybridus</i>	2.6 (0.9)	3.6 (1.1)	69.2 (20.1)
<i>Lupinus polyphyllus</i>	4.3 (1.4)	5.3 (1.8)	41.1 (10.1)
<i>Aquilegia vulgaris</i>	2.9 (0.4)	3.6 (0.6)	41.5 (8.1)
<i>Pelargonium graveolens</i>	5.9 (1.5)	9.4 (2.0)	148.2 (15.2)
<i>Nymphaea odorata</i>	0.8 (0.1)	1.1 (0.2)	9.9 (3.0)
<i>Hyacinthus litwinovii</i>	2.8 (0.9)	3.5 (1.2)	118.9 (19.2)
<i>Prunus laurocerasus</i>	2.0 (0.4)	2.4 (0.4)	13.4 (2.8)
<i>Rhododendron azaleastrum</i>	2.2 (1.1)	2.9 (1.5)	40.0 (21.4)

<i>Ilex aquifolium</i>	1.2 (0.2)	1.4 (0.2)	9.0 (2.0)
<i>Hosta sieboldiana</i>	2.0 (0.4)	2.5 (0.5)	28.8 (11.5)
<i>Citrus sinensis</i>	1.6 (0.4)	2.1 (0.5)	31.9 (18.6)

220

221 *Surface chemistry*

222 ATR-FTIR was used to identify the major classes of chemical species within the first
223 few microns of the adaxial surfaces of the leaves (Figures 3 and 4). All the leaf spectra generally
224 featured a relatively strong and broad hydrogen-bonded OH stretching band centred at 3300
225 cm^{-1} (Peak A, Figure 3). For the *Prunus laurocerasus* and *Hosta sieboldiana*, this band was
226 noticeably weak relative to the C-H stretching bands (centred at ca. 2900 cm^{-1}). However, for
227 the *Nymphaea odorata*, the OH band was more intense than the C-H band. The *Gladiolus*
228 *hybridus*, *Citrus sinensis*, *Hyacinthus litwinovii*, and *Pelargonium graveolens* leaves had an
229 OH band that was of near equal intensity to the C-H band. The OH band can be assigned to
230 alcohols, carboxylic acids, and water. All the leaves exhibited two bands at 2916 and 2846 cm^{-1}
231 ¹ (asymmetric (ν_{as} CH₂) and symmetric (ν_s CH₂) methylene C-H stretching, respectively),
232 which corresponded to the non-polar hydrocarbon compounds on their surfaces. The
233 accompanying methylene C-H deformation (scissoring (ν_s CH₂)) and C-H rocking (ν CH₂)
234 bands centred at ca. 1450 and 720 cm^{-1} , respectively, were also evident. All the leaves featured
235 carbonyl (C=O) bearing species that generally absorbed at 1735 cm^{-1} , indicating the possible
236 dominance of ester-based compounds present in the leaf composition. A broad collection of
237 bands centred at ca. 1630 cm^{-1} was also evident on all the leaves which can be assigned mainly
238 to H-O bending modes of the water molecule. In all cases, except *Hosta sieboldiana* and to a
239 lesser extent *Prunus laurocerasus*, the absorbance of this band was indicative of the OH
240 stretching band. In the exceptional cases of *Hosta sieboldiana* and *Prunus laurocerasus*, there
241 was significant confounding with other chemical species that absorbed in the same region. For

242 *Hosta sieboldiana*, there was a strong and sharp band (1640 cm^{-1}) in this region. For all the
 243 leaf surfaces, a band at 1055 cm^{-1} was detected which could correspond to the C–O stretching
 244 of primary alcohols that are present.

245
 246 **Figure 3.** ATR-FTIR spectra showing OH and CH stretching and fingerprint regions of the
 247 leaf surfaces. Note that absorbance has been normalised to the C-H stretching bands to
 248 compensate for differences in effective contact area.

249

250 A band at 1032 cm^{-1} was detected on the *Lathyrus odoratus*, *Nymphaea odorata*,
251 *Hyacinthus litwinovii*, *Prunus laurocerasus*, *Ilex aquifolium*, *Hosta sieboldiana*, and *Citrus*
252 *sinensis* leaf surfaces, which could correspond to the C–O stretching of secondary alcohols.
253 Interestingly, pronounced splitting of the $\nu_s\text{ CH}_2$ and νCH_2 bands was detected in the spectra
254 of the *Gladiolus hybridus*, *Hosta sieboldiana*, *Lupinus polyphyllus*, and *Lathyrus odoratus*,
255 which can be assigned to the presence of highly crystalline wax structures (Figure 4). This was
256 also evident on the *Aquilegia vulgaris* and *Pelargonium graveolens* leaf surfaces but to a lesser
257 extent. The *Ilex aquifolium* and *Prunus laurocerasus* surfaces exhibited a single νCH_2 band at
258 719 cm^{-1} , which could indicate a disordered (liquid-like) arrangement of long alkyl chains. The
259 *Hyacinthus litwinovii* and *Nymphaea odorata* showed weak $\nu_s\text{ CH}_2$ and $\nu\text{ CH}_2$ bands hindering
260 detection of splitting. The *Hosta sieboldiana* differed from the other surfaces in that it also
261 demonstrated a $\nu_{\alpha s}\text{ CH}_2$ band at 2925 cm^{-1} and a C=O peak at 1640 cm^{-1} . Overall with regards
262 to the surface chemistries, the molecules observed on all the surfaces were those likely to be
263 related to the cutin structure of the surface.¹⁴ The results demonstrate that the main differences
264 in the surface chemistry were related to the disordered arrangement of wax-like chains (*Prunus*
265 *laurocerasus* and *Hosta sieboldiana*), in addition to the C=O and $\nu_{\alpha s}\text{ CH}_2$ group of the *Hosta*
266 *sieboldiana*.

268 **Figure 4.** C-H stretching, C-H deformation, and C-H rocking regions of the ATR-FTIR spectra
269 of the leaf samples showing variations in hydrocarbon content and structural ordering of wax
270 components (splitting of the ν_s CH₂ and ν CH₂ bands). Band I: carbonyl stretching from esters
271 and other carbonyl compounds; Band II: assigned to the H-OH bending vibration of water;
272 Bands III: various C-O stretching and C-N stretching vibrations. Lo: *Lathyrus odoratus*, Gh:
273 *Gladiolus hybridus*, Lp: *Lupinus polyphyllus*, Av: *Aquilegia vulgaris*, Pg: *Pelargonium*
274 *graveolens*, No: *Nymphaea odorata*, Hl: *Hyacinthus litwinovii*, Pl: *Prunus laurocerasus*, Ra:
275 *Rhododendron azaleastrum*, Ia: *Ilex aquifolium*, Hs: *Hosta sieboldiana*, Cs: *Citrus sinensis*.

276

277 *PCA and PLSR modelling of surface chemistry data*

278 The ATR-FTIR spectral data provided a basis for further statistical analysis of the
279 leaves. PCA was performed to analyse the results of the ATR-FTIR measurements to provide
280 a greater understanding of the relationships between the variables within the data.²⁹ The PCA
281 data is presented using score plots labelled by leaf type on the top and class (i.e level of
282 hydrophobicity) on the bottom (Figure 5), in addition to the loading plots of the first three
283 principal components (Figure 6). Analysing the loading plots (Figure 6) for each of the
284 principal components enabled the determination of which section(s)/peaks of the ATR-FTIR
285 spectra were influential in the relative positioning of the leaves in PCA and could be used to
286 relate back to the original spectra. Additionally, analysing the PCA when categorising the
287 samples according to their classification (surface wettability) revealed that the most
288 hydrophobic leaves shared common surface chemistry traits, demonstrated by being grouped
289 in close proximity with low intra-class variability (Figure 5, bottom). Based on their placement
290 in principal component 1 (PC1), it was concluded that the most hydrophobic leaves had strong
291 peaks pertaining to the OH stretching band, which could be observed when analysing the raw
292 data (Figure 5, bottom). The hydrophobic leaves also exhibited strong asymmetric (ν_{as} CH₂)

293 and symmetric (ν_s CH₂) methylene C-H stretching peaks at ~ 2916 and ~ 2846 cm⁻¹,
294 respectively, in addition to weak carbonyl ester peaks at ~ 1735 cm⁻¹. Furthermore, one of the
295 peaks that was a unique contributor to principal component 3 (PC3) included the split CH₂ peak
296 (~ 1475 cm⁻¹) methylene asymmetric (ν_{as} CH₂) C-H deformation which was only present in the
297 most hydrophobic leaves. This peak is indicative of non-cutin wax structures. In contrast, the
298 least hydrophobic leaves have highly-variable surface chemistry as measured by ATR-FTIR,
299 demonstrated by their scattered positions in the score plots. Interestingly, with the exception of
300 a few of the leaf samples, the hydrophobic and less-hydrophobic classified leaves could almost
301 be completely separated on the basis of their position according to PC3. This indicated that the
302 characteristics that contributed to this principal component could be used to distinguish
303 between these classifications and that their profile/values for these bands and corresponding
304 functional groups were very important in determining the hydrophobicity of a surface.

305

306 **Figure 5.** Score plots labelled by leaf type (top) and class, i.e. hydrophobicity, (bottom) of PC1
 307 vs PC2 (left) and PC1 vs PC3 (right) for the PCA of the ATR-FTIR spectra.

308
 309 **Figure 6.** Loading plots for the PCA of the ATR-FTIR spectra of the first three PCs. PC1 (top),
 310 PC2 (middle), and PC3 (bottom).

311
 312 Assessing the data by leaf type, it was clear that the ATR-FTIR of *Prunus laurocerasus*
 313 and *Ilex aquifolium* were very distinct from each other, as well as the other leaves in terms of
 314 the components that contribute to PC1 (Figure 5, top). Additionally, the *Hosta sieboldiana*
 315 was different from the other leaves (ν_{as} CH₂, C=O) that contributed to PC2. On determination
 316 of which areas of the ATR-FTIR spectra had distinct loadings for PC2 compared to the other
 317 PCs, it was observed that PC2 featured (among others) peaks at 2925 and 1640 cm⁻¹
 318 (downwards), and was the only PC that had notable influence by peaks in the 800-650 cm⁻¹
 319 range (Figure 6 middle). In contrast to the other leaf samples, *Hosta sieboldiana* exhibited a
 320 notable peak centred at ~2925 cm⁻¹ shouldering the ν_s CH₂ band (ca. 2916 cm⁻¹) and was the
 321 only leaf to exhibit a sharp absorption at 1640 cm⁻¹. Furthermore, the *Hosta sieboldiana* leaves

322 showed a very strong peak in the C-H rocking (νCH_2) region at $\sim 720\text{ cm}^{-1}$, an area that also
323 influences PC2 and further accounts for its marked positioning in PC2 away from other leaves.

324 While differences in various methylene frequencies were largely demonstrated by PC2,
325 the broad hydrogen bonded OH stretching band centred at 3300 cm^{-1} was a main contributor to
326 PC1 (Figure 6, top). As such, the positioning of the species along the horizontal axes of all the
327 score plots in Figure 5, representing PC1, was demonstrative of the strength of this peak. As
328 aforementioned, this peak was very weak for *Prunus laurocerasus* which explains its leftmost
329 position in the PCA score plots. Furthermore, this peak was also weak for the *Ilex aquifolium*
330 and *Hosta sieboldiana*, and thus they were also positioned on the left side in PC1. In contrast,
331 the *Nymphaea odorata* had the most prominent OH stretching band, accounting for its
332 rightmost positioning in PC1. The H-O bending modes at ca. 1630 cm^{-1} also contributed to
333 PC1, with lower intensity peaks differentiating *Prunus laurocerasus* and *Ilex aquifolium* from
334 the other samples. It can be surmised that PC1 was mostly influenced by ATR-FTIR peaks
335 attributable to O-H bands (stretching ~ 3300 and 1630 cm^{-1}), while PC2 was most influenced
336 by C-H methylene-related bands.

337 In addition to the PCA, further statistical analysis was performed using PLSR to model
338 the leaves WCA, and hence their surface wettability from the ATR-FTIR measurements. To
339 the authors knowledge, this was the first time that such a model has been implemented on a
340 complex biological system, whereby an attempt using such a system was used to determine if
341 it was possible to relate surface chemistry and WCA. It was found that the PLSR model was
342 able to account for $\sim 95\%$ of the variation in WCA with eight components. This showed that
343 extremely variable data was able to be explained by the developed model, indicating a high
344 level of applicability of such a system to analyse complex data. Analysing the loading plot
345 (Figure S1) for the first three principal components for the model (PC1, 85%, black solid line;
346 PC2, 8%, red dashed line and PC3, 5%, green dotted line), observations could be made about

347 the influence of various bands in the ATR-FTIR spectra that were most influential to this
348 model, in relation to the WCA of the leaf surface. As seen following PCA, PC1 for this model
349 was strongly influenced by the prominent OH stretching band centred at 3300 cm^{-1} , whilst PC2
350 was largely influenced by this peak but also the asymmetric and symmetric methylene CH_2 C-
351 H stretching peaks at $\sim 2916\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 2846\text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively. These bands within the loading
352 plots were the main contributors to these principal components which attests to their
353 importance and influence on the WCAs. Validation of the resulting regression model from this
354 analysis indicated very good correlation ($R^2 = 0.86$) between measured and predicted values,
355 indicating its potential for predicting surface hydrophobicity from ATR-FTIR spectra of a
356 given surface (see Figure S2 for the plot depicting the performance of the PLSR model).

357

358 DISCUSSION

359 Overall, there were some clear demarcations in the surface properties and composition
360 of the leaf samples. The *Lathyrus odoratus*, *Gladiolus hybridus*, and *Lupinus polyphyllus* were
361 the most hydrophobic with ΔG_{iwi} values of -91.7 , -91.3 , and -74.7 mJ/m^2 , respectively. Their
362 surface properties fitted with the Cassie-Baxter model of self-cleaning surfaces and they shared
363 common traits such as high S_a , S_q , and S_{pv} values, and low γ_s^{LW} , γ_s^{AB} , and γ_s^- components.
364 However, the surface topography of the *Lathyrus odoratus* and *Lupinus polyphyllus* was
365 characterised by platelet-like features, whereas the *Gladiolus hybridus* surface was populated
366 by a homogenous distribution of raised nodules. The presence of wax nanocrystals was also
367 evident on all three surfaces. Furthermore, their ATR-FTIR spectra exhibited splitting of the ν_s
368 CH_2 and νCH_2 bands. This indicated hydrocarbon wax crystallisation, which was in agreement
369 with the SEM images that showed distinct wax crystallisation on their surfaces. Thus, it
370 appeared that a high degree of surface roughness and the presence of a dense population of wax
371 nanocrystals corresponded to a very hydrophobic leaf surface. However, it did not appear that

372 the shape of the surface features distinctly influenced its hydrophobicity. This fits with the
373 Cassie-Baxter model whereby air (or gas) pockets may be trapped in the cavities of a rough
374 surface, resulting in a hydrophobic surface due to a composite interface with air pockets trapped
375 under the droplet.³⁰ It has also been suggested that nanoroughness is required to support
376 nanodroplets.^{31,32} Thus, it might be likely that an interplay of all these factors resulted in the
377 most hydrophobic surfaces, although the exact parameters that impact this effect are still
378 unclear.

379 The *Aquilegia vulgaris* was the fourth most hydrophobic surface and had greater γ_s^{AB}
380 and γ_s^- components, as well as less splitting of the ν_s CH₂ and ν CH₂ bands compared to the
381 three most hydrophobic leaves. The *Pelargonium graveolens* was the fifth most hydrophobic
382 surface and the only one with distinct trichomes. The *Pelargonium graveolens* had higher γ_s^{LW} ,
383 γ_s^{AB} , and γ_s^+ components than the four most hydrophobic surfaces which is likely influenced by
384 the trichomes on its surface. Godeau et al.³³ observed that the trichomes on *Echeveria pulvinata*
385 leaves were hydrophobic, whilst the surface from which the trichomes protruded was
386 hydrophilic. Water droplets may also rest on the trichomes as perfect spheres which means they
387 can easily run off the leaves.¹

388 The surfaces with intermediate hydrophobicity (*Nymphaea odorata*, *Hyacinthus*
389 *litwinovii*, *Prunus laurocerasus*, and *Rhododendron azaleastrum*) had mostly featureless
390 topographies, with the exception of the *Hyacinthus litwinovii* (platelet-like features).
391 Furthermore, there were no clear trends in their surface roughness or physicochemical values.
392 From the analysis, it was expected that the *Nymphaea odorata* would have been more
393 hydrophobic. However, the *Nymphaea odorata* surfaces used in this work had very few
394 topographical features. Additionally, compared to the other leaves, the *Nymphaea odorata*
395 surface exhibited intense OH stretching bands in the ATR-FTIR results, which would render
396 the surface more polar, and hence less hydrophobic. This effect may have been due to the age

397 of the leaf,^{2,34} thus suggesting that further studies are required to determine the surfaces of
398 leaves over time with respect to changes in their self-cleaning and water repellent properties.

399 The PCA identified the *Prunus laurocerasus* and *Ilex aquifolium* surfaces as being
400 chemically different to the other leaves. Both these surfaces demonstrated disordered (liquid-
401 like) arrangements of long alkyl chains which may have contributed to their differentiation in
402 the PCA. The least hydrophobic surfaces, the *Ilex aquifolium*, *Hosta sieboldiana*, and *Citrus*
403 *sinensis*, had the lowest ΔG_{iwi} values of -6.0, -5.7, and -2.3 mJ/m², respectively. These surfaces
404 also had the highest γ_s , γ_s^{AB} , and γ_s^- values. Differentiation in the surface topographies of the
405 three least hydrophobic leaves was more complex compared to the more hydrophobic surfaces.
406 However, the S_a and S_q values of the surfaces were generally lower than the other plant surfaces
407 with the exception of the *Nymphaea odorata* and *Prunus laurocerasus*. Both the *Ilex*
408 *aquifolium* and *Citrus sinensis* had surfaces with subtle features. Waxes may influence the
409 chemical difference in the leaves, and may be detected using FTIR, even if they occur as filling
410 material within the basic cutin network (intracuticular) rather than being present on top of the
411 cuticle (epicuticular).³⁵

412 The *Hosta sieboldiana* was an anomaly among the leaf samples as it exhibited distinct
413 surface features characterised by platelet-like protrusions, but was the second most wettable
414 surface. It also had a high γ_s^- value, in addition to a higher energy shoulder on the ν_{as} CH₂ band
415 and a strong sharp absorption at 1640 cm⁻¹ that was not present in any of the other spectra. This
416 peak can be attributed to C=O carbonyl groups present, which demonstrated polar attributes.
417 These features were further highlighted in the PCA, particularly with regard to the positioning
418 within PC2. The ATR-FTIR spectrum of the *Hosta sieboldiana* exhibited a shoulder on the
419 methylene C-H stretch at ~2925 cm⁻¹, which indicated that different hydrocarbons were present
420 in this species. This was represented in the PCA through the distinct positioning away from the
421 other species. These hydrocarbons may be associated with polar areas that could contribute to

422 the high γ_s^- values. Furthermore, in the H-OH bend band, the *Hosta sieboldiama* had another
423 absorption (1640 cm^{-1}) superimposed within the spectra, which was also accompanied by a
424 small doublet peak at 787 and 777 cm^{-1} . These peaks may be assignable to amine or amide
425 moieties which contributed to the high γ_s^- values recorded. These observations are likely to be
426 related to the presence of polar domains on the *Hosta sieboldiama* leaf, that in this case, had a
427 dominant effect on surface hydrophobicity rather than the surface topography.

428 The leaf surfaces studied in this work exhibited a range of different properties and yet
429 all were water repellent and self-cleaning. An elegant explanation was offered by Zhang et al.³⁶
430 as to why droplets on surfaces with features that are associated with the highly adhesive Wenzel
431 state can also be self-cleaning, like those surfaces that display the typical Lotus attributes
432 associated with the Cassie-Baxter state. It is known that on surfaces consistent with Cassie-
433 Baxter properties, self-cleaning is achieved due to low contact angle hysteresis and small
434 hydrodynamic resistance. Zhang et al.³⁶ further suggested that on surfaces in the Wenzel state,
435 small neighbouring droplets can coalesce into bigger ones, and the corresponding release of
436 surface energy results in a transition to the Cassie-Baxter state, and therefore self-cleaning
437 action is achieved.

438 Two methods of additional statistical analysis, PCA and PLSR, were used to explore
439 and enhance the relationship between the surface chemistry characteristics, as measured using
440 ATR-FTIR, and the surface wettability. PCA is an excellent and powerful tool to detect any
441 underlying clusters and groupings in the data when analysing the entire surface chemistry
442 profile. Additionally, as this technique does not make any assumptions about the data, nor does
443 it take into account existing classifications, any notable patterns and trends found using this
444 unsupervised approach can be confidently surmised to exist based on the ATR-FTIR spectra,
445 not their classification. Differences seen between sample classes (i.e. hydrophobic vs less
446 hydrophobic surfaces and different species) and the contributing factors to those differences

447 provide insight into what distinguishes them. In our presented analysis, we were able to not
448 only identify characteristics of hydrophobic leave surfaces and what are common features
449 amongst leaves of this type but we were also able to identify species that were particularly
450 unique and what about them was so discernible (i.e. *Prunus laurocerasus* and *Ilex aquifolium*).
451 This analysis was based solely off the surface chemistry ATR-FTIR spectra and clearly
452 demonstrates the influence surface chemistry has on the wettability of leave surfaces and it is
453 not just the surface physicochemical properties and topography that dictate hydrophobicity of
454 leaf surfaces.

455 Similar to PCA, the PLSR model was used to analyse the entire ATR-FTIR spectra,
456 although this model was concerned with equating the quantitative variable, WCA, as a critical
457 measure of surface wettability. The PLSR model found similar bands in the ATR-FTIR to be
458 the most important at influencing surface wettability. Furthermore, the presented PLSR model
459 showed excellent performance in validation (using a leave-one-out technique) and based on
460 these results, it could be suggested that leaf WCA (i.e. hydrophobicity) can be predicted using
461 ATR-FTIR surface chemistry data. As such, this finding has the potential to change the way in
462 which surface chemistry is viewed in the design of new materials based on plant-related natural
463 surfaces. This is the first time such an analysis has shown the importance of surface chemistry
464 in a range of leaf types and our produced model can be utilised to investigate and predict the
465 water contact angle of a range of biological surfaces.

466

467 **CONCLUSIONS**

468 The physicochemical, chemical, and topographical properties of leaves obtained from
469 twelve diverse plant varieties were examined and the results demonstrated that the most
470 hydrophobic surfaces had low carbonyl species, ordered platelet-like structures, high roughness
471 values, high γ_s and γ_s^{LW} values, and low γ_s^{AB} and γ_s^- values. However, regardless of the surface

472 properties, all the leaves were self-cleaning. Using PCA, when categorising the samples
473 according to their chemical classification, it was observed that the more hydrophobic leaves
474 shared common surface chemistry traits, demonstrated by being grouped in close proximity
475 with low intra-class variability. In contrast, the less hydrophobic leaves had highly-variable
476 surface chemistry as measured by ATR-FTIR. Nevertheless, this variability in surface
477 chemistry was able to accurately model, through PLSR, leaf water contact angle with excellent
478 ability. This is first time that the importance of surface chemistry in a range of leaf types has
479 been demonstrated. As such, these results may change the way that surface chemistry is viewed
480 in the design of new biomimetic materials based on plant surfaces. Furthermore, the presented
481 model could be used for the fast screening and determination of the water contact angles of a
482 range of biological surfaces.

483 Extensive work has been carried out on fabricating surfaces with well-defined
484 topographical features to produce hydrophobic and self-cleaning properties. However,
485 examples taken from nature clearly demonstrate that less hydrophobic, almost featureless
486 surfaces may also possess self-cleaning and non-wetting properties. A complete understanding
487 of the interactions between the magnitude and shape of surface topography, chemistry, and
488 physiochemistry, in addition to their influence on the self-cleaning action of surfaces has still
489 not been elucidated. In future work, we intend to design novel surfaces based on these
490 parameters and assess their self-cleaning properties in a range of experimental assays to
491 determine their use in specific, applied applications.

492

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496

497 **ASSOCIATED CONTENT**

498 The Supporting Information is available free of charge at

499 Table providing surface free energy components of test liquids; Graphs predicting the
500 WCAs from the ATR-FTIR using PLSR.

501

502 **CONFLICTS OF INTEREST**

503 The authors declare no competing financial interest.

504

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